

TRAINING NEEDS OF SECONDARY SCHOOL LEAVERS IN THE EFFECTIVE USE OF ONLINE TEST ASSESSMENT FOR ENTRY INTO HIGHER INSTITUTION

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Abstract:

The study was carried out to identify the training needs of secondary school leavers in the effective use of online test assessment for entry into higher institution. The design of the study was survey research design. Five research questions guided the study. The study was carried out in Akwanga Local Government Area of Nasarawa State. Population for the study was 1032, sample for the study was 232 made up of 200 secondary school leavers and 32 internet tutors using proportionate random sampling technique. A structured questionnaire was used for the data collection. The instrument was face validated by three experts, one from Data Perfect Computers Centre Akwanga and two from Computer Education Department, college of Education, Akwanga. Data collected were analysed using weighted mean to answer the research question, and t-test statistics clusters had their reliability coefficients ranged from 0.82 to 0.86 respectively. It was found out that Secondary School leavers needed training on the five clusters in 61 competencies on the use of internet for success in online test assessment. It is recommended that computer training centres and institution with computer training facilities should use the identified competencies by this study for training secondary school leavers for success in online test assessment for job application or entry into higher institution.

Keywords: online test assessment; secondary school leavers; need; training; effective; assessment

1. Introduction

Assessment is a means of determining the achievement or performance of an individual or worth of a program. Assessment in the view of Audu (2008) is a form of evaluation that uses collected data for estimating the worth, quality and effectiveness of a program. In Ombugus (2013), assessment refers to a process of determining the performance of a student's skills by asking the student to perform tasks that require those skills. Earlier, Nwachukwu (2015) defined assessment as the consideration and judgment of students' skills or knowledge competence. Assessment of students in institutions of learning either for promotion to the next level or entry into higher institutions has usually been carried out manually through written or oral examination. In this study, assessment is the use of internet to determine the performance of secondary school leavers in external examination usually conducted by Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB) for helping tertiary institutions such as universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education determine and select qualified secondary school leavers for admission into their various programs of learning. The assessment that is of great concern to this study is the one focused on the use of electronic technology such as the internet. With the development in technology, assessment of learners becomes easier through electronic means known as internet or online assessment.

Online test assessment is a web based application that establishes a network between the institution, staff and students. Online test assessment according to Robin (2010) is the process used for measuring certain aspect of information which is delivered through a computer connected to the internet. Online test is used primarily to measure cognitive abilities, demonstrating what has been learned after a particular educational event has occurred such as the end of an instructional unit. Institutions log onto their website to set questions of their choice for any student. The questions and answers that have been attempted by the students are then evaluated and scores saved. The scores can be retrieved from the computer by the internet assessor for the determination of the performance of the secondary school leavers to be assessed with regards to qualification and suitability for entry into an institution or job application.

Secondary school leavers in the view of Onwuka (2003) are those individuals who have completed their senior secondary school certificate program and some who may continue their studies in higher institution or may decide to enter into occupational field. In this study, secondary school leavers are individuals that has completed a six year study in a secondary school, and passed West African Senior School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) or National Examination Council (NECO) with a minimum of five credit, and qualified to sit for examination for entry into higher institution like

University, Polytechnics, and College of Education or seeking for job application in any organization or federal government parastatal that require such qualification, but they are assumed by this study to have low or negligible experience in the use of internet for answering examination questions for the purpose of entering into higher institution or seeking for job. The reason for this assumption is the scarcity of internet facilities in most of the secondary schools attended by these secondary school leavers.

The Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB), and other recognized internet examination organization or consultant are hired and trusted with the responsibility of carrying out online test assessment to secondary school leavers. Secondary school leavers or applicants into tertiary institution are made to answer their examination questions usually called online test or computer base test examination (CBTE) for ease of marking electronically and control of other factors such as delay in releasing examination result and examination malpractice. Currently, Examination bodies expected the teaching and learning in schools to match with the assessment method which is the use of online test assessment. In the area of this study, the expectations of the examination bodies are far from been real because of certain constraints which include absence of computer base training, use of ICT tools to tackle problems on the internet after graduation. Therefore secondary school leavers' who have the intention of seeking admission into tertiary institution or job application through online test assessment, and be successful in acquiring knowledge and skill in all these areas of Computer, they need training.

Need according to Procter (1995) is a condition of lacking or wanting something necessary or very useful. In view of Omeh (2010) a need is something that is required to fill an existing essential gap. In this study, need is the ability of secondary school leavers to operate and manage internet test items for success in online test assessment. Secondary school leavers in this study need to possess knowledge and skills in booting on a computer system, operating the input and output devices, software application for browsing and downloading materials from the internet, time and facility management for accessing internet test items and confidence building attitude. For these secondary school leavers to be successful in these areas they need training.

Training as stated by Aliyu (2011) is the organizational effort aimed at helping an employee to acquire basic skills required for the efficient execution of the function for which he was hired. McNamara (2009) stated that training involves an expert working with learners to transfer to them certain areas of skills to enable them improve in their current job. Training enhances the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and attitude by an employee that leads to his growth and development within the organizational hierarchy. This type of training is applicable to all area of technology where the user is

ignorant. In the area of this study, secondary school leavers have been used to pen and pencil examination throughout their study in the secondary school which was administered by examination bodies like WASSCE (West African Senior School Certificate) and NECO (National Examination Council). Technology is now exposing and changing the process of examination from pen and pencil to computer and internet based assessment for recruiting school leavers either for job application or entry into tertiary institution. This development has demonstrated significantly the importance of internet assessment, and secondary school leavers' departure from pen and pencil examination to internet based facilities by most examination bodies for which many secondary school leavers are ill-prepared or very ignorant. Most of the secondary school leavers are intelligent enough to pass the WASSCE and NECO examination through pen and pencil, but they lack the confidence in attempting and passing online examination for entry into higher institution or seeking for job application after graduation. The issue here is the inability of these secondary school leavers to interact confidently and intelligently with the technology provided for the online test assessment by the internet assessors. Therefore secondary school leavers' need effective training to enable them become familiar, confident, and skilled in the application of computer and internet to enable them interacts fully with these devices during online examination. To be effective means to be very successful in the direction a teacher will want a student or learner to succeed. This success can only be achieved through training which is needed by secondary school leavers in online test assessment in the mastery of the competencies on the components of the computer already stated above. Therefore, it is necessary to identify the competencies in areas of computer as stated in this study where secondary school leavers need training for success in online test assessment for entry into higher institution.

The major purpose of the study therefore, is to determine the training needs of secondary school leavers in Nasarawa State on the effective use of online test assessment for entry into higher institutions. Specifically, the study identified the training needs of secondary school leavers in: Booting on a computer system, Operating of input and output devices, Software application for browsing and downloading material from the internet, Time and facility management for accessing internet test items, and Confidence building attitudes for success in online test assessment.

Methodology

Five research questions were answered by the study and five hypotheses tested. The design of the study was descriptive survey. The study was carried out in Akwanga

Local Government Area of Nasarawa State. Population for the study was 1032 made up of 1000 secondary school leavers and 32 internet tutors. Sample for the study was 232 made up of 200 secondary school leavers and 32 online instructors using proportionate (20%) random sampling technique to select the sample for the secondary school leavers while the entire population of the internet tutors was involved in the study. A 61 structured questionnaire item derived from literature was used as an instrument for collecting data. Each questionnaire item had four responses options of Highly Needed (HN), Averagely Needed (AN), Slightly Needed (SN), Not Needed (NN) with assigned values of 4,3,2,1, respectively. It was face validated by three experts one from Data Perfect Computers Centre, Akwanga and two from Computer Science Education Department, College of Education Akwanga. The reliability of the questionnaire items was achieved through the use of Cronbach-Alfa to determine the internal consistency of each item. The Alfa co-efficient obtained for each area is as follows: Booting on the computer system -0.82, Operating input and output devices -0.85, Software application for browsing and downloading -0.86, Time and facility management -0.83, and Confidence building attitude -0.84. The questionnaire was used to collect data through the help of two research assistants. The data collected were analysed using weighted mean to answer the research questions, and t-test statistics to test the hypotheses of no significant difference at 0.05 level of significance and relevant degree of freedom.

The real limit of numbers was used to take a decision on the mean as follows: 4.00 – 3.50 (HN), 3.49-2.5 (AN), 2.49-1.5 (SN), 1.49-1.00 (NN); any item with a mean of 1.50 or above indicated that the item is needed for training school leavers for success in online test assessment. In deciding on hypothesis tested on the mean ratings of the responses of internet tutors and secondary school leavers the P-value was used. Any item whose P-value is greater than or equal to 0.05, indicated that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of the responses of the two groups of respondents on the training needs of secondary school leavers on the item. Therefore the hypothesis of no significant difference was accepted for that item.

Results

The result for this study was obtained from the research questions answered and hypotheses tested through the analysis of the data collected.

Research Question 1:

What are the competencies in booting on a computer system on which secondary school leavers needed training for success in online test assessment?

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of secondary school leavers and internet tutors on the competencies in booting on a computer system on which secondary school leavers needed training for success in online test assessment. The data for answering research question and testing hypothesis one are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean ratings and t-test analysis of the responses of secondary school leavers and internet tutors on the competency in booting on a computer system. IT: n=32, SSL: n=194

S/N	Item Statement	$\bar{X}_g$	$\bar{X}_{sl}$	$\bar{X}_t$	S^2_{sl}	S^2_t	P-value	RQ
1.	Turn on the power button on a computer system	3.88	3.87	3.89	0.33	0.31	0.78	HN
2.	Observe if the system is loading and setting the registers to specific values	3.47	3.50	3.47	0.50	0.50	0.78	AN
3.	Check if the CPU jumps to address the BIOS	3.66	3.65	3.67	0.48	0.47	0.87	HN
4.	Observe if the BIOS runs post (power on self-test) and other necessary check on the computer system	3.46	3.46	3.45	0.56	0.58	0.92	AN
5.	Observe if the BIOS locates runs from MBR and locates the secondary boot loader.	3.42	3.17	3.62	0.70	0.68	0.01	AN
6.	Check if primary boot loader runs from MBR and locates the secondary boot loader.	3.53	3.53	3.54	0.56	0.58	0.92	HN
7.	Observe if the secondary boot loader loads the operating system and the windows logo is displayed on the screen of the monitor of the computer system.	3.49	3.46	3.50	0.67	0.65	0.80	AN
Cluster Information		3.55	3.52	3.59	0.54	0.53	0.72	HN

Keys: $\bar{X}_g$ = Grand mean, $\bar{X}_t$ = mean of Internet tutors, $\bar{X}_{sl}$ mean of secondary school leavers, S^2_t = Variance of Internet tutors, NS = Not Significant, HN = Highly Needed, AN = AN Needed, S^2 = Significant, IT = Internet tutor, Secondary School Leavers, RQ = R Question, Ho = hypotheses.

Table 1 revealed that the mean value is 3.55 on the cluster information on the competency in booting on a computer system and is greater than 1.50; this indicated that secondary school leavers needed training on the competency in booting on a computer system.

The data in Table 1 also revealed that the cluster information on the competency in booting on a computer system had its p-value as 0.72 and is greater than 0.05 indicating that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of the responses of

secondary school leavers and internet tutors on the competency in booting on a computer system.

Research Question 2:

What are the competencies in operating input and output devices on secondary school leavers needed training success in online test assessment?

Hypothesis 2:

There is no significant difference between the mean rating of secondary school leaver internet tutors on the competencies in on input and output devices on which secondary school leavers needed training for success internet test assessment. The data for answering research question testing hypothesis two were presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean rating and t-test analysis of the responses of secondary school leavers and internet tutors competency in operating input and output devices. IT: n=32, SSL: n=194

S/NO	Item statement	$\bar{X}_g$	$\bar{X}_{st}$	X_t	S^1_{sl}	S^1_t	P-value	RQ	HO
1.	Connect the power cable to the source of power	3.80	3.81	3.82	0.39	0.38	0.86	HN	NS
2.	Connect the VGA (Video Graphic Adapter) cable from the monitor to system unit	3.38	3.47	3.30	0.49	0.49	0.87	AN	NS
3.	Locate and press the power button to start up the monitor	3.65	3.52	3.80	0.55	0.50	0.03	HN	S
4.	Identify if monitor screen display the desktop icons.	3.63	3.62	3.67	0.55	0.51	0.61	HN	NS
5.	Locate and press the buttons at the base of the monitor to adjust the volume, contrast, brightness and colour of the monitor	3.48	3.43	3.49	0.66	0.61	0.62	AN	NS
6.	Click on left button of the mouse to select an item	3.58	3.59	3.61	0.49	0.48	0.83	HN	NS
7.	Click on the left-button of mouse twice to open a selected item.	3.55	3.56	3.58	0.50	0.49	0.70	HN	NS
8.	Click on the left button of the mouse to pop up a small dialog box	3.55	3.56	3.58	0.50	0.49	0.70	HN	NS
9.	Handle the mouse correctly	3.48	3.46	3.52	0.56	0.58	0.64	AN	NS
10.	Press F1 to display the help dialog box	3.28	3.31	3.32	0.78	0.72	0.93	AN	NS

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11.	Press F10 to activate the menu bar option	3.25	3.05	3.49	0.67	0.65	0.01	AN	S
12.	Press ctrl + shift + Esc key to open window task manager	3.33	3.37	3.36	0.70	0.67	0.94	AN	NS
13.	Press Alt + TAB key to switch to another running program	3.43	3.43	3.47	0.71	0.68	0.75	AN	NS
14.	Press window logo + E key to display windows explorer	3.30	3.31	3.33	0.59	0.59	0.84	AN	NS
15.	Press window logo to display the start menu	3.53	3.43	3.50	0.61	0.62	0.59	HN	NS
16.	Press ctrl + C key to copy a document	3.38	3.43	3.50	0.61	0.62	0.59	AN	NS
17.	Press ctrl + X key to cut a document	3.38	3.43	3.40	0.61	0.61	0.79	HN	NS
18.	Press window logo + P key to start the print manager	3.45	3.33	3.60	0.61	0.62	0.02	AN	S
19.	Press window logo + D key to minimize all open window and display the desktop.	3.45	3.43	3.50	0.61	0.62	0.59	AN	NS
20.	Press shift + Delete key to delete an item permanently.	3.45	3.46	3.50	0.67	0.65	0.80	AN	NS
Cluster Information		3.46	3.44	3.51	0.60	0.58	0.58	HN	NS

Keys: $\bar{X}_g$ = Grand mean, X_t *mean* of Internet tutors, X_{sI} mean of secondary school leavers, S^2_{sI} = Variance of secondary school leavers, S^2_t Variance of Internet tutors, NS = Not Significant, HN = Highly Needed, AN = Averagely Needed, S* = Significant, IT = Internet tutor, SSL Secondary School Leavers, RQ Research Question, Ho hypotheses.

Table 2 revealed that the mean value is 3.46 on the cluster information on the competency in operating input and output devices and is greater than 1.50; this indicated that secondary school leavers needed training in operating input and output devices.

The data in Table 2 also revealed that cluster information on the competency in operating input and output devices had its P-value as 0.58 and is greater than 0.05 indicating that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of the responses of secondary school leavers and internet tutors on the competency in operating input and output devices on a computer system.

Research Question 3:

What are the competencies in software application for browsing and downloading materials from the internet on which secondary school leavers needed training for high performance in online test assessment?

Hypothesis 3:

There is no significant different in the mean rating of secondary school leavers and internet tutors on the competencies in software application for browsing and downloading materials from the internet on which secondary school leavers needed training for high performance in online test assessment. The data for answering research question and testing hypothesis were presented in table 3.

Table 3: Mean ratings and t-test analysis of the responses of secondary school leavers and internet tutors on the competency in software application for browsing and downloading materials from the internet. IT: n=32, SSL: n=194

S/N	Item Statement	$\bar{X}_g$	$\bar{X}_{st}$	X_t	S^2_{st}	S^2_t	P-value	RQ	HO
1.	Get on the web with a computer system	3.88	3.87	3.39	0.33	0.31	0.78	HN	NS
2.	Open internet explorer or Mozilla	3.70	3.71	3.73	0.52	0.48	0.84	NH	NS
3.	Enter a web address	3.33	3.31	3.35	0.53	0.52	0.66	AN	NS
4.	Locate search engine (e.g.) yahoo, goggle.	3.58	3.62	3.61	0.55	0.52	0.90	AN	NS
5.	Navigate through web pages	3.50	3.53	3.54	0.56	0.58	0.92	HN	NS
6.	Search the internet for information	3.30	3.11	3.55	0.78	0.72	0.01	AN	S
7.	Type needed concept into the search engine.	3.18	3.21	3.21	0.65	0.66	0.95	AN	NS
8.	Download material/document from the internet through appropriate path.	3.50	3.53	3.54	0.56	0.58	0.92	HN	NS
9.	Save web pages as a file.	3.40	3.46	3.42	0.56	0.58	0.71	AN	NS
10.	Store or transfer the downloaded materials into a storage devices e.g. flash	3.38	3.27	3.62	0.70	0.68	0.00	AN	S
11.	Open multiple web pages of a time	3.33	3.37	3.36	0.65	0.63	0.90	AN	NS
12.	Browse for relevant material	3.40	3.40	3.44	0.66	0.65	0.73	AN	NS
13.	Download PDF files successfully	3.33	3.37	3.37	0.70	0.70	0.97	AN	NS
14.	Create and send email messages	3.25	3.31	3.28	0.69	0.68	0.85	AN	NS
15.	Logout from the internet	3.48	3.46	3.52	0.56	0.58	0.64	AN	NS
Cluster Information		3.43	3.43	3.46	0.60	0.59	0.71	AN	NS

Keys: $\bar{X}_g$ grand mean, $\bar{X}_t$ mean of Internet tutors, X_{st} mean of secondary school leavers, S^2_{st} Variance of secondary school leavers, S^2_t Variance of Internet tutors, NS Not Significant, HN = Highly Needed, AN = Averagely Needed, S* Significant, IT Internet tutor, SSL Secondary School Leavers, RQ Research Question, Ho hypotheses.

Table 3 revealed that the mean value is 3.43 on the cluster information on the competency in software application for browsing and downloading materials and is greater than 1.50; this indicated that secondary school leavers needed training in software application for browsing and downloading.

The data in Table 3 also revealed that the cluster information on the competency in software application for browsing and downloading materials from the internet had its P-value as 0.71 and is greater than 0.05 indicating that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of the responses of secondary school leavers and internet tutors on the competency in software application for browsing and downloading materials from the internet.

Research Question 4:

What are competencies in time and facility management for accessing internet test items on which secondary school leavers needed training for effectiveness in online test assessment?

Hypothesis 4

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of secondary school leavers and internet tutors on the competencies in time and facility management on which secondary school leavers needed training for effectiveness in online test assessment. The data for answering research question and testing hypothesis are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Mean rating and t-test analysis of the responses of secondary school leavers and internet tutors on the competencies in time and facility management. IT: n=32, SSL: n=194

S/N	Item Statement	Significant difference in the mean rating of the item statement							RQ	HO
		$\bar{X}_g$	$\bar{X}_{sl}$	Xt	S ¹ _{sl}	S ¹ _t	P-value			
1.	Set realistic goal in internet test assessment.	3.85	3.87	3.36	0.33	0.34	0.89	HN	NS	
2.	Plan for the future when assessing the internet.	3.25	3.28	3.27	0.63	0.56	0.94	AN	NS	
3.	Monitor activities as you assess the internet	3.68	3.52	3.82	0.55	0.49	0.02	HN	S	
4.	Create an environment conducive for effectiveness in the internet environment	3.45	3.43	3.50	0.66	0.65	0.61	AN	NS	
5.	Set priorities for yourself as you	3.35	3.34	3.40	0.78	0.73	0.65	AN	NS	

assess the internet items.

6.	Carry out activity around those priorities	3.53	3.56	3.56	0.56	0.58	0.96	HN	NS
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Cluster Information	3.51	3.50	3.48	0.58	0.55	0.67
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Keys: $\bar{X}_g$ grand mean, X_t *mean* Internet tutors, X_{sl} mean of secondary school leavers, S^2_{sl} Variance of secondary school leavers, S^2_t Variance of Internet tutors, NS Not Significant, HN = Highly Needed, AN Averagely Needed, S* Significant, RQ Research Question, Ho hypotheses.

Table 4 revealed that the mean value is 3.51 on the cluster information on the competencies in time and facility management and is greater than 1.50; this indicated that secondary school leavers needed training in time and facility management.

The data in Table 4 also revealed that the cluster information on the competency in time and facility management had its P-value as 0.67 and is greater than 0.05 indicating that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of secondary school leavers and internet tutors on the competency in time and facility management.

Research Question 5:

What are the competencies in confidence building attitudes on which secondary school leavers needed training for success in online test assessment?

Hypothesis 5:

There is no significant difference in the mean rating of secondary school leavers and internet instructors on the competency in confidence building attitude on which secondary school leavers needed training for success in online test assessment. The data for answering research question and testing hypothesis five are presented in table 5.

Table 5: Mean ratings and t-test analysis of the responses of secondary school leavers and internet tutors on the competencies on confidence building attitude. IT: n=32, SSL: n=19

S/N	Item Statement	$\bar{X}_g$	$\bar{X}_{sl}$	X_t	S^2_{sl}	S^2_t	P-value	RQ	HO
1.	Accept the truth about himself both good and bad, and be ok with it	3.90	3.90	3.91	0.29	0.28	0.91	HN	NS
2.	Surround oneself with likeminded and supportive people	3.33	3.51	3.25	0.53	0.52	0.01	AN	S
3.	Start with achieving small and easy goal and work up to larger goal	3.35	3.37	3.41	0.79	0.77	0.80	AN	NS
4.	Recognize and release destructive habits from the past.	3.45	3.46	3.48	0.56	0.54	0.87	AN	NS

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5.	Focus on the positive not the negative.	3.38	3.59	3.62	0.61	0.60	0.76	AN	NS
6.	Provide positive feedback to learners when appropriate	3.70	3.55	3.84	0.48	0.43	0.03	HN	S
7.	Provide suitable environment and facility for learners to learn.	3.23	3.28	3.24	0.58	0.56	0.75	AN	NS
8.	Correct learners gently when they make mistake rather than bullying..	3.33	3.37	3.37	0.70	0.70	0.97	AN	NS
9.	Set realistic goal for each learner	3.50	3.53	3.54	0.56	0.58	0.92	HN	NS
10.	Create an open and positive environment for learning	3.30	3.37	3.34	0.70	0.70	0.79	AN	NS
11.	Be proud of students when they record achievement	3.38	3.41	3.41	0.66	0.64	0.92	AN	NS
12.	Encourage students to try harder when they fail.	3.53	3.56	3.56	0.56	0.58	0.96	HN	NS
13.	Use appropriate teaching strategies that provide an opportunity for equal participation.	3.48	3.50	3.52	0.71	0.68	0.84	AN	NS
Cluster Information		3.45	3.49	3.49	0.59	0.58	0.73		

Keys: Xg grand mean, Xt mean of Internet tutors, XsI mean of secondary school leavers, Sst Variance of secondary school leavers, S^t Variance of Internet tutors, NS Not Significant, HN=Highly Needed, AN Averagely Needed, S* Significant, RQ Research Question, Ho hypotheses.

Table 5 revealed that the mean value is 3.45 on the cluster information on the competencies in confidence building attitude and is greater than 1.50; this indicated that secondary school leavers needed training in the competency in confidence building attitude.

The data in Table 5 also revealed that the cluster information on the competency in time and facility management had its P-value as 0.73 and is greater than 0.05 indicating that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of the responses of secondary school leavers and internet tutors on the competency in confidence building attitude.

Discussion of Findings

The study found out that secondary school leavers needed training for success in online test assessment in the following competencies: 7 competencies in booting on the computer System, 20 competencies in operating input and output devices, 15 competencies in software application for browsing and downloading material from the

internet, 6 competencies in time and facility management and 13 competencies on confidence building attitude.

These findings were in agreement with the submission of Omeh (2010) who stated that for individual to perform the operation of booting the computer system effectively they must be competent in 7 competencies such as Turning on the power button on the computer system among others. Also in Time and Facility Set priorities for yourself as you assess the internet items and 5 others. The findings was supported by the submission of Marley (2014) that effectiveness in interaction with the computer for success in any examination required confidence building attitude in 13 competencies like; create an open and positive environment for learning and 12 others.

The findings of the hypothesis revealed that there is no significant difference in the mean rating of the internet tutors and secondary school leavers on 52 out of 61 competencies for operating computer on which secondary school leavers need training for success in online test assessment. This revealed that the respondent in operating computer for success in online test assessment did not significantly influence the responses on the 52 items, but probably did significantly on nine items.

Conclusion

It was generally observed in the area of this study that secondary school leavers' who have been used to pen and pencil examination usually encounter difficulties in interacting with the computer in any examination for success in online test assessment, and therefore usually recorded low scores, though they may be competent intellectually. This study was carried out to identify the competencies required for operating the computer on which secondary school leavers needed training for success in online test assessment. The study also found out that secondary school leavers needed training for success in online test assessment. The study also found out that secondary school leavers needed training in 61 competencies in 5 areas of computer for success in online test assessment for job application or entry into higher institution. It is therefore recommended that the findings of this study be used by organized computer training centre, higher institution, internet tutors for training secondary school leavers for success in online test assessment.

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